

EFFECTIVE TIME MANAGEMENT: METHODS AND MEANS OF ACHIEVING MAXIMUM PRODUCTIVITY

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Annotation: In this article, you can find out what are the ways and means of making the most of time; the role of time management in personal development, goals and objectives in the meaningful Organization of Youth time and how they determine the agenda of celebrities.

Key words: time management, culture, time management, "Pareto rule", Jim Loer, Tony Schwartz, institution, production, need, digital transformation.

In an era when time is globalizing, changing, life is moving at a rapid pace, each person tries to further enrich the purpose, meaning, dreams of his life, to cultivate his consciousness and thinking, his worldview in a more information stream.

Everyone who comes into this world will not stop trying even so that the next one is better today. In life, spiritually and financially, he wants to create good conditions for himself, this is the basic need of a person, so is it easy to be perfect in each area and have time for several jobs at the same time?

Time management is the time management techniques and methods that are counted. This is self-organization and self-management. Time management helps a person or companionship plan time and save resources. For example, if you are overwhelmed with work and do not know what to do in the first place, the Eisenhower matrix will help you determine which tasks are urgent and important, and which are just distractions. While the famous "Pareto rule" it is important that we know that, of

course, 20% of the action according to it gives 80% of the result. The more we can do, the better and more productive the quality of our work and life in general will change.

In the context of digital transformation and the acceleration of change, managing the exact time will help you concentrate on your goals, stay on track and ultimately not remain a pilot in the labor market.

Almost all available time management methods consist of three components:

- 1) priority;
- 2) planning;
- 3) systematization;

Most of the time management methods rely on systematization and priorities, and only a small part is a complex combination of all three principles. When managing time, first of all, a person should be strong, healthy full of energy.

"Full power life. In the book Power Management-the key to high efficiency, health and happiness, Jim Loer and Tony Schwartz say that there are several types of power. These are:

- physical;
- emotional;
- mental;
- spiritual;

plays a big role in time management. Because a person is able to control sleep quality nutrition, self-confidence, effective time management and creativity, interests, his energy and energy increase, and productivity and efficiency increase to the maximum. Let's look at the planning of the day according to the power level through a simple example:

- Creativity power (preferably from 4: 00 to 11 :00)
- Social capacity (preferably from 18: 00 to 23 :00)
- Power for communication (calls, emails, messages, -preferably from 14:00 to 17:00)

- Strength to learn (any time except half a day)
- Physical strength (sports-better from 12:00 to 14:00)

The higher the power level during a person's life, the higher the quality of their implementation, the higher the skills they develop as part of their time planning. Looking at the agenda of successful people:

- Warren Buffett wakes up at 6: 45 am and begins the day reading newspaper books.
- Richard Brenson wakes up at 5: 00 and goes in for sports. From starting work , first, he spends his time in the family circle.

Successful individuals do not control their time, they usually act actively when the power level is high, and in this way work on permanence. Today, the concept of timer management has become a very popular and relevant topic in improving the efficiency of time management. Timeout is management, that is, a person has time to do a lot of work in a short time. It is the ability of a person to manifest himself both in his work and in his family, in his personal growth in society.

By studying time management, a person first of all achieves an increase in work efficiency. As a result, it turns out additional time for other personal affairs, intellectual development or leisure. Constant management of time sets the stage for success as a consequence of the efficiency achieved. In order for a person to achieve success in his work activities and life, he must first of all determine his goal. After all, life without a goal cannot be established. The goal is bamisoli, like a light that illuminates human life. As long as that light is in our lives, we will continue to live and not stop moving. with the most efficient use of time , we follow our dreams intensively.

What is time management, that is, effective time management? Timer-control- (English-time-time, management-means management) - time efficient management technology, Time organization, its effective use texnologiyasidir. In this consciously controls the time when a person does a certain job. Often, time management does not take into account the main factors that contribute to the effectiveness of a person. We

are not an ideal 24-hour car or robot day. It we need to plan, taking into account our feelings, strength and willpower.

Schedule important work for the most productive part of the day, instead of focusing on diqatt on timeout management. Don't forget to relax. Form the habits you follow.

There is such a wonderful and invaluable sentence in our people: "You have a reduction at every sunset." From the point of view that time reflects our existence in this world, it is much more valued than money, or rather-incomparable. Humanity compares time with flow river. No, on the contrary, for whom time passes quickly, the miles in his life also move fiercely. On the contrary, counting time as a blessing it makes rational use of every moment of it, and the one who is grateful is considered to get rid of the attitude of rushing and not having time.

In place of the conclusion, it should be said that a person cannot control his time, but control himself and his behavior. Due to self-control, esa also makes good use of its time. Achieve dreams and goals that are fundamental in life. We always have time, we have a lot of time, deymiz. To he does not wait for us, but can walk equally. Get rid of words like "tomorrow", "not now", "I'm tired" that immerse us in our psyche lganimizdagina. Biz we need to change and edit our imagination, our concepts in relation to time. Then our love for life will increase.

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